

A PERMEABILITY COMPUTATIONAL MODEL BASED ON MESO-SCALE GEOMETRY: CONSIDERING COMPACTION DEFORMATION OF PREFORM

Jianjun Jiang¹, Xing Chen¹, Guoli Deng¹

¹ Shaanxi Engineering Research Center for Digital Manufacturing Technology, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, P.R. China, jianjun@nwpu.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

Compaction deformation of the preform to a desired fiber volume fraction has a significant influence on the permeability which is a key parameter for resin to infiltrate the preform in liquid composite molding (LCM) process. In this paper, the unified mathematical model for global permeability for considering the compaction of yarn in the preform unit-cell was established in the multilayer fabric. The model focused on a detailed meso-scale description for different zones of characteristic yarn arrangement in the unit-cell structure, which taken into account the local permeability distribution as a function of geometrical yarn parameters due to the mold compression. The global permeability was then modeled as a mixture of permeabilities of different zones with the electrical resistance analogy. Meanwhile, the effect of internal parameters of preform unit-cell, including the shape and dimensions of the tows and the channels, with the compaction on the global permeability of fabric was analyzed. The results indicated that the global permeability of fabric is very sensitive to the estimated value of the mean channel width and with the increase of compression force, the global permeability gradually decreases. The prediction model was correlated with experimental data available, and satisfactory agreement was observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, liquid composite molding (LCM) processes such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum-assisted resin injection (VARI) molding have become increasingly popular to fabricate large and complex parts in marine, aircraft, automotive industries [1-3]. These processes offer several advantages over the conventional composite molding, including lower costs and improved manufacturing quality. Generally, the LCM processes take place in three major steps: forming the fiber-reinforcing preform, injecting the thermoset resin and curing. Permeability that determines the impregnation of the preforms with liquid resin is one of the most important parameters for numerical flow simulations, which can assist the designer in optimizing the injection process in order to design the mold and predict the resin flow in the mold [4,5]. As a consequence, the preform permeability is crucial to optimum process parameters for manufacturing processes to obtain high-quality products.

Nesting caused by layer shift is a geometric and mechanical phenomenon, which inevitably occurs during the process of ply stacking and has a great influence on the permeability of preforms [6]. It causes statistical distribution of the preform permeability on account of the change of the flow path [7]. Young et al. [8] developed an analytical model which taken into account the number of layers and phase shifted between adjacent layers to obtain statistical analysis on the out-of-plane permeability. Endruweit et al. [9] analysed the relation between permeability variations and geometrical fabric parameters, and obtained that nesting has an important influence on the permeability variations. The similar conclusions were also found that comparison of results generated with and without consideration of "structural" nesting indicates that this effect has a significant influence on the in-plane permeability, in particular along the preform 0° direction for triaxially braided reinforcements [10]. Additionally, Grujicic et al. [11,12] and Lekakou et al. [13] established numerical

models to predict the permeability of textiles with nesting. However, due to the complex yarn shapes in a deformed fabric and the multiple contact zones between the yarns, it is difficult to define a representative unit cell of a multi-layer composite with a compacted and nested unidirectional reinforcement[14]. Jiang et al. [15,16] developed analytical models to study the nesting on in-plane and out-of-plane permeability of unidirectional fabrics with minimum and maximum nesting, respectively.

In this article, the effect of layer shift on in-plane permeability of unidirectional fabrics was investigated experimentally and theoretically, respectively. Analytical model was established to predict in-plane permeability, which focused on a detailed meso-scale description for different zones of characteristic yarn arrangement in the unit-cell structure and taken into account the local permeability distribution as a function of geometrical yarn parameters due to the mold compression. And the experimental results were compared with the predictions from the analytical model.

2 THEORETICAL MODELING

Permeability that is the inherent properties of the preforms is only related to its fiber volume fraction, void distribution and yarn dimensions. In analogy to the electric resistance, the reciprocal of the preform permeability can be used to describe the resistance to the flow. Some scholars have carried out relevant theoretical researches [17,18]. When the flow resistances of the layers are in series, the flow rates in different zones add up to the total flow rate, as shown in Fig.1(a). Then the permeability of the preforms can be estimated as:

$$K = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{K_i} V_i \right)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Where K is the total permeability of the preforms, K_i is the permeability of zone i and V_i is the fiber volume fraction of zone i .

When the flow resistances of the layers are in parallel, the pressure differentials in different zones add up to the total pressure differential, as shown in Fig.1(b). Then the permeability of the preforms can be estimated as:

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i V_i \quad (2)$$

Fig 1: Schematic of the flow resistances of the unit cell considering they could be analogous to electrical resistance (a) series connection (b) parallel connection

Since the void shape of the fiber bundle is very complex, there is no direct analytical model to describe the impregnation behavior of the complex channel. It is estimated based on the simplified geometry illustrated in Fig.2. The total cross-sectional area of voids is expressed as a rectangular gap with height Δw and width a , and the following relation can be obtain:

$$\Delta w = \left(1 - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) h' \quad (3)$$

Fig 2: Yarn cross section and simplification of void geometry

Based on the model investigated by Endruweit [18], the equivalent permeability of each gap can be estimated by:

$$K_{gap,x} = K_{gap,y} = \frac{(\Delta w / 2)^2}{12} \quad (4)$$

The permeability of the yarn is calculated based on the equations proposed by Gebart[19],

$$K_{yarn \parallel} = 8r_f^2(1 - V_b)^3 / (C_{\parallel}V_b^2) \quad (5)$$

$$K_{yarn \perp} = C_{\perp} r_f^2 (\sqrt{V_{b,max} / V_b} - 1)^{5/2} \quad (6)$$

Where $K_{yarn \parallel}$ and $K_{yarn \perp}$ are the permeability of the flow along and perpendicular to the filament axis, respectively. C_{\parallel} , C_{\perp} and $V_{b,max}$ are geometrical constants for the two types of yarn arrangement summarized in Table 1. r_f is the filament radius. V_b is the fiber volume fraction of the yarn, and has the following relation [20].

$$V_b = \frac{h}{h'} V_0 \quad (7)$$

Where h is the thickness of the yarn. V_0 is the initial fiber volume fraction. h' is the thickness after deformation.

Fiber arrangement	C_{\parallel}	C_{\perp}	$V_{b,max}$
Quadratic	57	$\frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{\pi}{4}$
Hexagonal	53	$\frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}}$

Table 1: Parameter values of permeability equations

The nesting of fiber bundles is one of the key factors that affect the fiber impregnation behavior. Depending on the unidirectional fabric architecture, the layer shift is divided into the following stages to study the effect of internal parameters of preform unit-cell, including the shape and dimensions of the tows and the channels, with the compaction on the global permeability of fabric in the interval $[0, L/2]$.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the fabric unit cell can be decomposed into different zones according to local fiber volume fraction. It is assumed that yarns in the contact parts will carry load, thus will deform and be compacted first [21]. The fiber volume fraction of zones 1 and 5 increase during the process of compaction, when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$. While that of zones 2 and 4 remain due to no compaction in these area. Then the resistances of the unidirectional fabrics in x-direction are in series; the

resistances of the unidirectional fabrics in y-direction are in parallel, as shown in Fig.4. The permeability can be expressed as follows:

$$K_x = \left(\frac{1}{K_x^1} \frac{a/2}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^2} \frac{e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^3} \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^4} \frac{e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^5} \frac{a/2 - \Delta x}{a+e} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$K_y = K_y^1 \frac{a/2}{a+e} + K_y^2 \frac{e}{a+e} + K_y^3 \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + K_y^4 \frac{e}{a+e} + K_y^5 \frac{a/2 - \Delta x}{a+e} \quad (9)$$

Where Δx is the horizontal translation in x-direction. a is the long axe of the yarn. e is the gap between adjacent yarns.

Substituting Eqs. (4)-(6) into K_x^i and K_y^i , the in-plane permeability of the unit cell with shift range $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$ can be obtained.

Fig 3: Unit cell of unidirectional composites when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$, decomposed into five different zones.

Fig 4: Schematic of the flow resistances of the unit cell when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$ (a) series connection in x-direction (b) parallel connection in y-direction

When $e \leq \Delta x \leq a/2$, the fiber volume fraction of the zones 1, 3 and 5 increase during the process of compaction. While that of zones 2 and 4 remain due to no compaction in these areas, as shown in Fig.5. Then the permeability can be expressed as follows:

$$K_x = \left(\frac{1}{K_x^1} \frac{a/2}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^2} \frac{e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^3} \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^4} \frac{e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^5} \frac{a/2 - \Delta x}{a+e} \right)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$K_y = K_y^1 \frac{a/2}{a+e} + K_y^2 \frac{e}{a+e} + K_y^3 \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + K_y^4 \frac{e}{a+e} + K_y^5 \frac{a/2 - \Delta x}{a+e} \quad (11)$$

Substituting Eqs. (4)-(6) into K_x^i and K_y^i , the in-plane permeability of the unit cell with shift range $e \leq \Delta x \leq a/2$ can be obtained.

Fig 5: Unit cell of unidirectional composites when $e \leq \Delta x \leq a/2$, decomposed into five different zones.

When $a/2 < \Delta x \leq L/2$, the fiber volume fraction of zones 2 and 4 increase during the process of compaction. While that of zones 1, 3 and 5 remain due to no compaction in these areas, as shown in Fig.6. Then the permeability can be expressed as follows:

$$K_x = \left(\frac{1}{K_x^1} \frac{\Delta x - a/2}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^2} \frac{a - \Delta x}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^3} \frac{e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^4} \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + \frac{1}{K_x^5} \frac{a/2 - \Delta x + e}{a+e} \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$K_y = K_y^1 \frac{\Delta x - a/2}{a+e} + K_y^2 \frac{a - \Delta x}{a+e} + K_y^3 \frac{e}{a+e} + K_y^4 \frac{\Delta x - e}{a+e} + K_y^5 \frac{a/2 - \Delta x + e}{a+e} \quad (13)$$

Substituting Eqs. (4)-(6) into K_x^i and K_y^i , the in-plane permeability of the unit cell with shift range $e \leq \Delta x \leq a/2$ can be obtained.

Fig 6: Unit cell of unidirectional composites when $a/2 < \Delta x \leq L/2$, decomposed into five different zones.

Comparing Eqs.(8), (10) and (12), it must be noted that the variety of layer shift results in the different permeability of every two-layer fabric. Therefore, in analogy to the electric resistance, the in-plane permeability of multilayer fabrics can be written as follows:

$$K_x = \frac{\sum K_x^j h_j'}{\sum h_j'} \quad (14)$$

$$K_y = \frac{\sum K_y^j h_j'}{\sum h_j'} \quad (15)$$

Where h_j' is the distance between the layer j and $j+1$. K_x^j and K_y^j are the permeability of the layer j in x and y direction, respectively.

If every shift between adjacent layers is previously obtained, the analytical permeability of multilayer fabrics can be calculated. However, layer shifting is hardly obtained in actual process. When the total thickness is kept constant, the average thickness per layer \bar{h} instead of interlayer distance h' is substituted into Eqs. (14) and (15). The in-plane permeability of multilayer fabrics can also be written as follows:

$$K_x = \frac{\sum K_x^j}{n} = E(K_x^j) \quad (16)$$

$$K_y = \frac{\sum K_y^j}{n} = E(K_y^j) \quad (17)$$

Where $E(K_x^j)$ and $E(K_y^j)$ are the mathematical expectations of K_x^j , K_y^j , respectively.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 MATERIALS

The textile composite reinforcement used in this paper is E-glass unidirectional fabric EDW442 as presented in table 2. The tested fluid is the epoxy resin 5015 with a viscosity of 800 mPa·s at the room temperature.

Material	EDW442
Diameter of fiber filament	16 μ m
Filament count	2200
Height of fiber bundle	400 μ m
Width of fiber bundle	2.23mm
Gap between adjacent yarns	350 μ m

Table 2: Test material data

3.2 TEST PROCEDURE

For the unidirectional fabrics described above, the unsaturated in-plane permeability was measured in radial flow experiments at a constant injection pressure of 0.1 MPa, as shown in Fig.7. The unidirectional fabrics were placed and held stationary by compacting them to obtain desired fiber volume fraction. Then the tested fluid was injected through the fabrics with a radius of 200 mm. The camera was used to record the advancement of the flow when the fabrics was impregnating. Then the in-plane permeability of the unidirectional fabrics was obtained by following Chan and Hwang's method [22].

Fig 7: Experimental apparatus schematic

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 8 presents the in-plane permeability of E-glass unidirectional fabric EDW442 with respect to the average thickness per layer and shifting ratio ($\Delta x / (L/2)$). As expected, the permeability of the two-layer fabric tends to decrease with decreasing the average thickness of each layer. However, as the shifting ratio increases, different directions have different trends, which mean that the layer shift has different effect on permeability. Now, fixing the average thickness per layer at 0.35mm, consider in permeability with changes of the shifting ratio. The permeability that changes as the shifting ratio can be obtained, as shown in Fig.9.

Fig8: The change of permeability with respect to average thickness per layer and layer shift for (a) K_x , (b) K_y

Fig9: Permeability as a function of layer shift when average thickness per layer was fixed at 0.35mm for (a) K_x , (b) K_y

In x-direction, the fabric permeability is principal dominated by the fiber volume fraction where the flow resistances of the layers are in series. As the shifting ratio increases, the fiber volume fraction decreases and the fabric permeability increases. The permeability increases rapidly and the fabrics offer big resistance to the flow, when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$. However the permeability increases slowly because the pure void does not exist in zone 3, when $e \leq \Delta x \leq L/2$.

In y-direction, it is no doubt that fluid tends to flow through the empty flow channel made by the layer shift in that internal flow in principle seeks to look for a way with the lowest flow resistance. The presence of pure voids has a significant effect on permeability where the flow resistances of the layers are in parallel. When $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$, although the fiber volume fraction decreases, the permeability decreases because the void spaces in zone 3 is decreasing. When $e \leq \Delta x \leq L/2$, the permeability increases because the pure void does not exist and the fiber volume fraction decreases.

The validity of the model is illustrated by Fig.10, which compares experimental and analytic data on the nesting of unidirectional fabrics. Better agreement is found between analytic and experimental values with increasing the number of layers. For K_x , the relative errors between experimental and theoretical average permeabilities are 21.1% for 6 layers, 17.9% for 8 layers and 13.5% for 10 layers,

respectively. It can be seen that the relative errors of K_y is larger in comparison to K_x . For K_y , the relative errors between experimental and theoretical average permeabilities are 36.4% for 6 layers, 29.6% for 8 layers and 22.8% for 10 layers.

Fig10: Comparison of analytically calculated average permeability values with experimental data for (a) K_x (b) K_y

The reason is that the gap between adjacent yarns has been assumed to be constant in the models. However, in the actual process, the fiber bundle cross-section and the gap are very complex and will change with the compression. For K_y , the pure voids are the main factor affecting the permeability value. The existence of large pure void makes the experimental value of permeability larger than the theoretical average; For K_x , the transverse permeability is principal dominated by the fiber volume fraction. In the model, it is assumed that the volume fraction of the fiber bundle is different after deformation, but the nesting will make the partial fiber volume fraction large. Therefore the existence of large fiber volume fraction makes the experimental value of permeability smaller than the theoretical average.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the unified mathematical model for global permeability for considering the compaction of yarn in the preform unit-cell has been established to predict the in-plane permeability of multilayer unidirectional fabrics. The global permeability was modeled as a mixture of permeabilities of different zones with the electrical resistance analogy. Meanwhile, the effect of internal parameters of preform unit-cell, including the shape and dimensions of the tows and the channels, with the compaction on the global permeability of fabric was analysed. It could be seen that the permeability K_x increases rapidly with increasing the layer shift, when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$ and increases slowly when $e \leq \Delta x \leq L/2$. K_y decreases rapidly when $0 \leq \Delta x \leq e$ and increases slightly when $e \leq \Delta x \leq L/2$ with increasing the layer shift. Successful permeability predictions in comparison with experimental data were achieved.

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